

AI based vulnerability assessment pipeline for microservices: A pragmatic approach

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Executive Summary

The purpose of the ACME project was to develop an AI-driven automated tool to generate vulnerability assessment test cases (MicroSecAI) for REST API-based applications. As industry increasingly adopts a shift-left approach to building resilient products, automation plays a crucial role in achieving this goal. By integrating AI, the complexity of generating vulnerability test cases can be significantly reduced, allowing software developers and cybersecurity engineers to perform their tasks more accurately and efficiently while producing secure products. The overall objectives were (i) to reduce the complexity of vulnerability testing, (ii) to integrate security with the shift-left, (iii) to minimize the efforts for manual vulnerability assessment, and (iv) to bring automation through AI.

The most significant outcome of the ACME project is the proof-of-concept implementation of MicroSecAI. The overall pipeline and architecture of MicroSecAI is designed, which is based on a combination of cybersecurity frameworks and AI models, including OWASP, GPT models, the Hypothesis library, Postman data models, the Newman CLI tool, and several third-party Python libraries to ensure feasibility and modularity. The core architecture follows a modular design, enabling the development of a scalable REST API-based application that is further extended with CLI functionality. All REST endpoints are exposed through a dedicated PoC web interface. The modular configuration also allows new or updated vulnerability sets to be seamlessly integrated into the existing system, ensuring long-term adaptability and maintainability.

The ACME project demonstrated that AI-driven automation can effectively support the shift-left approach by reducing complexity, improving scalability, and accelerating vulnerability assessment, while still requiring human oversight and organizational support to achieve secure-by-design software development.

1 Introduction

Microservices-based architecture has emerged as a leading choice for organizations seeking faster time-to-market and enhanced productivity. According to DORA (DevOps Research and Assessment) report, companies adopting microservices experience an average 60% increase in productivity (Global, 2024). Unlike monolithic systems, microservices are designed as a collection of small, independent, and loosely coupled services. Each service can be deployed, scaled, and updated independently, allowing businesses to respond quickly to evolving market demands (Di Francesco, Lago, & Malavolta, 2019). However, this flexibility introduces new security challenges. Every microservice expands the attack surface, making robust cybersecurity practices essential at every stage of the software development life cycle (SDLC).

Security measures such as source code analysis, vulnerability analysis, software composition analysis, and adherence to secure design principles are critical in minimizing the risk of cyberattacks. A growing trend in the industry is the adoption of the “shift-left” approach, where security and vulnerability detection techniques and tools are integrated early in the development process as shown in Figure 1 (Phan, Nguyen, & Nguyen, 2023). By identifying and addressing threats at the initial stages, organizations can reduce the likelihood of data breaches, safeguard sensitive information, and mitigate potential legal and compliance risks. In current practical use, various tools, standards, and best practices are employed to identify and eliminate vulnerabilities. However, most of these operate in isolation, resulting in gaps or “blind spots”, in vulnerability assessment. Additionally, security engineers often create vulnerability test cases manually, which are typically executed in isolation or depend heavily on the engineers’ interpretation and technical expertise. This fragmented approach can leave certain hidden vulnerabilities undetected, which may ultimately serve as the root cause of successful exploitation by the attackers.

Figure 1: Software Development Life Cycle in shift-left approach, cybersecurity perspective

Vulnerability assessment is a technical process which should be taken by the security professionals to avoid exploitation but in shift-left approach, software developers also perform these activities using automated tools. Manual testing, which follows standard processes is a time-consuming process. A lot of work has been done in this domain, for example various tools and frameworks like BURP-Suit (Portswigger, 2025), sqlmap (Stampar, 2025), mitmproxy (Mitmproxy, 2025), jwt_tool (?), OWASP Top 10 (OWASP, 2025), SANS CWE 25 (CWE, 2025) and postman (Postman, 2025) are being used to test microservices against vulnerability, but all are used in isolation and required certain level of technical skills. To overcome such issues, a new approach needs to be tested and investigated therefore in this project, MicroSecAI, we adopted AI based approach to automate the vulnerability assessment test cases generation and execution process. In addition, AI will also interpret the outcome of the identified vulnerability for software engineers to fix it. Therefore, based on identified issues, in this paper, we will try to answer following

question “Which techniques enable the collaborative orchestration of multiple specialized AI and software modules in the vulnerability assessment process, and which models and metrics most effectively measure the performance of the resulting AI pipeline?” As we witnessed that the modern API-driven applications are increasingly targeted by sophisticated cyberattacks exploiting vulnerabilities listed in the OWASP Top 10 and other Vulnerability Lists. While OpenAPI specifications provide a structured view of API endpoints, existing automated security testing tools often lack full vulnerability coverage, effective fuzzing strategies, and the ability to produce actionable remediation guidance in natural language. Traditional pipelines also require significant manual intervention to parse specifications, generate comprehensive test cases, execute them, and interpret results, making them inefficient for continuous security testing in agile development cycles. Therefore, there is a need for an AI-driven system that autonomously:

- Parses OpenAPI specifications to generate high-coverage test cases targeting OWASP Top 10 vulnerabilities.
- Augments these test cases with fuzzing techniques to discover edge-case and zero-day vulnerabilities.
- Executes the tests and processes results automatically to detect vulnerabilities with high precision.
- Converts execution results into clear, actionable natural language recommendations for developers to fix identified security issues.
- Coordinates multiple specialized modules through robust communication protocols to enable end-to-end automation without manual coordination.

The challenge lies in designing an AI based architecture that ensures reliable communication, high vulnerability detection coverage, minimal false positives, and efficient execution, while producing developer-friendly remediation advice. To address these challenges, the ACME team designed a framework, MicroSecAI, which enables the automation of the vulnerability assessment process and brings agility to the microservice’s cybersecurity testing process. The MicroSecAI solution is based on the following core Principles:

Reduce Vulnerability Testing Complexity: Microservices enable rapid development and deployment by breaking applications into small, independent services. While this approach increases agility and productivity, it also significantly expands the attack surface, making comprehensive and continuous security testing indispensable.

Shift-Left Security Integration: Embedding security measures early in the software development lifecycle (shift-left approach) facilitates proactive identification and mitigation of vulnerabilities. Early detection reduces remediation costs, minimizes risks of breaches, and ensures compliance with regulatory standards.

Challenges of Isolated and Manual Vulnerability Assessment: Current vulnerability assessment tools operate largely in isolation and depend heavily on manual test case creation and execution. This fragmentation leads to coverage gaps, inefficiencies, and reliance on specialized expertise, which can allow critical vulnerabilities to remain undetected.

Automation Through AI: Leveraging AI-driven automation for generating, fuzzing, and executing test cases can overcome the limitations of manual processes. This approach helps in enhancing test coverage and accelerating vulnerability detection.

1.1 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Section 1 provides an overview of the report content and an introduction to the ACME (MicroSecAI) project, whereas Section 2 presents a comprehensive analysis of existing literature, approaches, and tools proposed, designed, and developed for REST API vulnerability assessment. Section Section 3 introduces the MicroSecAI data flow pipeline, which is further explained through the system architecture. The Proof-of-Concept is explained in Section 4, and the document is concluded in Section 5. Additional information is provided in Appendix A, which includes how to get the source code for local deployment and working OpenAPI JSON documents.

2 Background and State of the Art

In cybersecurity vulnerability assessment domain, there are various techniques are used to generate the vulnerability test cases but still these are in the evaluation phase since the threat landscape is changing with respect to the technological advancements. Following are the most used automated test-case generation and execution techniques are used by various tools vendors and cybersecurity engineers:

- **Fuzzing:** This technique generates random or semi-random inputs, mutation-based or generation-based (structured) vulnerability test cases. For example, Hypothesis is used for Python-related test case generation (hypothesis, 2025), Jazzer for Java-based applications (Jazzer, 2025), etc.
- **Symbolic and Concolic Execution:** In these techniques, analysts supply symbolic inputs and explore the program paths to derive concrete test inputs that target particular branches or conditions. This concept is described in (Ma, Fu, & Wang, 2022), which first generates paths, then performs a path evaluation function, and finally selects paths using a Path Selection Algorithm. Based on the selected paths, test cases are generated.
- **Search-based and Evolutionary Testing:** These techniques use genetic algorithms and evolutionary heuristics (e.g., aDynaMOSA, Adaptive Evolutionary Strategy in unit testing) to optimize coverage or fault detection (Grano, Laaber, Panichella, & Panichella, 2021).
- **Model-based Driven Approaches:** These techniques are mostly used in cybersecurity. A widely adopted industry approach is threat-model-driven test case derivation, especially in security and automotive contexts. It uses structured threat models, attack surfaces, and protocol models to derive test cases accordingly (Marksteiner, Priller, & Wolf, 2024).
- **Risk-based Prioritization / Coverage Criteria:** In this approach, specific areas or modules are selected based on risk, threat modeling, and impact, which is particularly important in vulnerability assessment. This is considered a foundational approach for risk-based software development, where cybersecurity and resilience are key functional requirements.
- **AI/ML/LLM-driven Approaches:** These techniques use machine learning for vulnerability detection or test generation. Many cybersecurity-focused AI models are developed to identify vulnerabilities in source code, generate application-specific test cases, and assist developers in creating unit tests.

Once the test cases are generated then a comprehensive test cases execution plan is required which is normally orchestrated using vulnerability orchestrator or third-party applications and tools. Execution platforms, scripting or orchestration are key to scale vulnerability testing because without such automated execution tools, test-case generation only covers part of the workflow and final report is missing.

2.1 General Automated Test Case Generation

Software engineering processes are becoming mature, and more software quality and cybersecurity testing is moving in the development phases to achieve multidimensional benefits like achieving software functional maturity and early detection of vulnerabilities to make it more resilient. Various techniques are used to generate test cases like structural testing, model-based testing, combinatorial testing, random/adaptive random testing. Some of these are explained

in the paper (Anand et al., 2013). Since our focus is on the automating vulnerability testcases generation and assessment therefore various tools are the key blocks of the playing field. For example, in (Bau, Bursztein, Gupta, & Mitchell, 2010), the author analysed leading commercial web vulnerability scanners, mostly used for black-box testing, and provided empirical insight to understand their scope, effectiveness and coverage scenarios. All these tools are developed based on some specific techniques and some of them are described in (Sotos Martínez, Villanueva, & Orellana, 2022), (Luo et al., 2022). Similarly some of the other approaches including genetic algorithm and AI based are presented in (Marksteiner et al., 2024), (Pelofske, Urias, & Liebrock, 2024)(Liu, Wang, Mateega, Georgescu, & Tang, 2025) (Mehendran, Tang, & Lu, 2025)

2.2 REST API Specific Automated Test Case Generation

Optimization of REST API-specific code coverage was explored in EvoMaster (Arcuri, 2022), where a search-based testing approach, the Many Independent Objective (MIO) algorithm, was adopted. Since the developers had full access to the source code, a white-box testing strategy was applied. The study demonstrated promising results, automatically identifying 80 real bugs across a limited number of REST APIs. With the advancement of AI, several tools now leverage machine learning techniques for automated test case generation. For instance, DeepREST employs Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) in a black-box setting, using reward-guided dynamic exploration to learn from valid input sequences and fault states, thereby generating realistic test cases that mirror real-world usage scenarios(Corradini, Montolli, Pasqua, & Ceccato, 2024). Similarly, documentation-guided fuzzing approaches have been proposed, where Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques are used to extract semantic and syntactic features from API documentation, combining them for intelligent fuzzing and vulnerability discovery. A wide range of open-source and commercial tools also support REST API and web application security testing. OWASP ZAP, one of the most widely used open-source tools, performs both active and passive scans to intercept REST API calls, injecting potentially malicious payloads into URLs, headers, and message bodies (zapproxy, 2025). It also supports fuzzing, with additional plugins enhancing its vulnerability testing capabilities. Burp Suite offers both free and commercial versions and automates scanning for injection, serialization, and deserialization vulnerabilities using mutation-based fuzzing (Portswigger, 2025). Metasploit Framework follows an exploit-driven testing methodology, generating payloads and chained exploits to uncover security flaws (metasploit framework, 2025). Postman provides both a GUI-based interface and a CLI tool for automated test execution and security scan orchestration, supporting script-based test collections for regression and functional validation(Postman, 2025). Finally, Schemathesis implements property-based testing through its Hypothesis libraries, enabling schema-driven fuzzing of OpenAPI/JSON definitions to automatically generate valid and invalid payloads (hypothesis, 2025). Together, these solutions demonstrate the evolution from traditional rule-based testing toward AI-augmented, context-aware, and schema-guided vulnerability assessment approaches for modern REST API ecosystems.

2.3 Role of AI in Automating Cybersecurity Test Cases Generation

A lot of modern web services rely heavily on REST APIs, with OpenAPI being the dominating specification. The widespread adoption of this standard has resulted in many proprietary black-box testing tools generating tests. These traditionally struggle with exhaustive testing of all input combinations, real-world parameters, often resulting in undetected failures, high manual effort,

and limited test coverage. To address the challenges, assistant tools have emerged to enhance REST API documents by leveraging natural language descriptions, in order to address complex scenarios regarding specific data formats or inter-parameter dependencies. Although Large Language Models (LLMs) have shown promising test-generation abilities, such as extracting information from the human-readable parts of the spec (e.g. name and description), their application to REST API testing has remained mostly unexplored until recently. A recent example (Stennett, Kim, Sinha, & Orso, 2025) brings the addition of using two Llama3-8b models, one for detecting inter-parameter dependencies and another for generating inputs - along with reinforcement learning to dynamically incorporate server feedback during testing. These models were fine-tuned using parameter and parameter dependency databases, increasing the success rate of creating valid inputs from 23% to 69%, also experimenting with quantization showing efficiency-accuracy tradeoff with smaller models performing well. This work also notes that recent introduction of Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA) techniques in fine-tuning, by which only a small set of model parameters are modified during training, significantly reduces computational and memory requirements while maintaining performance. An earlier example (Kim, Stennett, Sinha, & Orso, 2025), also attempting a holistic solution to the testing, by combining multiagent reinforcement learning (MARL) with a semantic property dependency graph (SPDG) and LLMs. The strategy is focused around using four different agents collaborating to optimize API exploration, with separate focuses on API, dependency, parameters, and values. A recent study (Barradas, Paes, & de Oliveira Neves, 2025) introduces RestTSLLM, which focuses on the creation of test scenarios and the definition of appropriate input data, proposes the use of Test Specification Language (TSL), which serves as a bridge between business requirements and automated testing by providing a high-level, declarative format for specifying test cases. Instead of writing low-level test scripts, users define inputs, expected behaviors, and outcomes in a structured, human-readable format. By abstracting the test logic from its implementation, TSL enables the automatic generation of test scripts for different platforms, making it particularly effective for validating APIs and complex systems through reusable and maintainable specifications. The TSL test cases are converted into functional integration tests and presented as examples to the (general, not fine-tuned) LLMs.

Collectively, these approaches demonstrate a shift from purely rule-based parameter-naïve testing toward hybrid systems that combine LLMs with reinforcement learning and structured specifications, enabling more comprehensive and efficient API security testing.

3 MicroSecAI – pipeline

Pipeline for MicroSecAI solution is shown in figure 2 and has following four main phases:

Figure 2: MicoSecAI pipeline and flow of processes to generate vulnerability assessment test cases

- (i) **Reconnaissance:** The reconnaissance process is based on two primary conditions. First, if the microservices already have descriptions available in the standard OpenAPI or Swagger format (hereafter referred to as the API description), the Vulnerability Test Case Generator can directly accept and process them. Second, if such descriptions are not available in the standard format, the developer or security engineer must employ external tools such as Burp Suite, mitmproxy, or mitmproxy2swagger to generate the required documentation. It is essential to ensure that these generated descriptions strictly conform to the OpenAPI or Swagger specification.
- (ii) **Processing:** The processing phase of MicroSecAI accepts the API description in OpenAPI format and validates it. Once validated, it is passed to the Vulnerability Test Case Generator, which uses an AI component to generate test cases against specified vulnerabilities. Since the focus is on identifying OWASP Top 10 vulnerabilities (OWASP, 2025), some or all of these vulnerabilities are passed to the AI component. The generated test cases are stored in a Postman-compatible format in a local file. Subsequently, the API specification is passed to the Vulnerability Fuzzy Test Case Generator, which generates edge-case test cases to evaluate REST APIs against input validation issues, buffer overflow attacks, and deserialization attacks. All outputs are aggregated into a single file in Postman format.
- (iii) **Execution:** The execution phase accepts all generated test cases and analyzes endpoint dependencies to generate a visual graph. The endpoints are then executed sequentially to obtain improved results. All responses are saved locally for report generation.
- (iv) **Interpretation:** This phase processes all responses and converts technical results into natural language that is easily understandable by developers.

3.1 MicroSecAI Architecture

Figure 3: Architecture of MicoSecAI and interaction between various components

The MicroSecAI pipeline is implemented using a modular design, relying heavily on existing off-the-shelf AI models and Python libraries. All components interact through well-defined interfaces, ensuring seamless communication across modules as shown in figure 3. AI modules communicate via standardized protocols that transport structured data objects necessary for each module to generate results. The overall MicroSecAI architecture is organized into four main layers, with each layer comprising multiple specialized modules designed to handle distinct responsibilities within the vulnerability assessment and test case generation workflow.

- Utility Layer:** This layer provides essential support functions for the vulnerability-assessment workflow. It is responsible for receiving API specifications (e.g., OpenAPI/Swagger), validating their structure, and preparing them for processing by the Engine modules through the API Description Handler. After the engines generate the vulnerability test cases in Postman-compatible format, this layer performs schema validation to ensure structural correctness and completeness. The resulting test cases are packaged as Postman collections, which developers can either download for manual execution or forward to the Dependency Extraction Module. This module automatically analyzes API paths, request–response relationships, and inter-endpoint data flows to generate a dependency graph. The graph enables optimal ordering of test execution, improving coverage and reducing false negatives. Additionally, the layer includes a Reporting Module that interprets raw test outputs and converts them into clear, developer-friendly descriptions, enabling efficient debugging and remediation.
- Engine Layer:** The Engine Layer contains the core intelligence of MicroSecAI and implements multiple AI-driven modules responsible for generating, optimizing, sequencing, executing, and interpreting vulnerability assessment test cases. These modules operate on validated API specifications and produce structured, executable postman collections

enriched with dependency mappings and automated insights. The key engine modules include:

- **Vulnerability Test Case Generation Engine:** This module receives the validated API description along with a selected set of vulnerabilities, either the complete OWASP Top 10 for REST APIs or a customized subset chosen by the engineer. It triggers the Compute Module to interact with the AI model using carefully engineered prompts that include global instructions, endpoint-specific details, and the targeted vulnerability set. Since test generation is computationally expensive, the module implements a caching/optimization strategy: endpoints with unchanged configurations are skipped, and only newly introduced or modified endpoints are processed. The engine then parses AI responses, applies rule-based normalization (e.g., removing JavaScript functions, fixing malformed payloads, ensuring environment variables are correctly referenced), and produces a clean, structured output ready for integration.
- **Fuzzy Test Case Generator:** Aligned with the Defense-in-Depth principle, this module generates property-based and fuzzing test cases to uncover deep and non-trivial vulnerabilities by injecting malformed, random, or boundary-breaking inputs into HTTP requests. Using the OpenAPI file as input, the module leverages Python's Hypothesis library to produce schema-aware fuzz tests, covering edge cases such as malformed JSON and nested JSON structures, extreme-length inputs, missing or unexpected properties, type violations, etc. This enables detection of time-limit failures, deserialization flaws, buffer overflows, and potential zero-days. All fuzz tests are stored in versioned, structured artifacts for traceability and reproducibility.
- **Dependency Extraction Module:** This module analyzes the OpenAPI specification along with the outputs of the previous two engines to construct a unified postman collection and generate an execution strategy. Because vulnerability assessment often requires calling endpoints in the correct order (e.g., authentication → token → protected resource), the module builds a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) of endpoint dependencies by analyzing JSON schema fields, nested structures, references (\$ref), array dependencies. It automatically detects circular dependencies, an indication of design flaws in the API specification. The engine then produces a topologically sorted execution plan, restructures test collections accordingly, and extracts all environment variables into a separate postman environment file.
- **Execution Engine:** This module receives the generated test case collection and the environment variable file (after the user fills in required values such as tokens, keys, or host URLs). It executes all test cases sequentially, following the dependency-aware order, and records every request/response pair along with metadata such as timestamps, status codes, and failure signatures.
- **Interpretation Engine:** Finally, this module processes the raw execution results and translates them into developer-friendly insights. It applies natural-language generation (NLG) rules to summarize issues, highlight potential vulnerabilities, and provide actionable remediation guidance. Additionally, it generates structured PDF reports (for stakeholders, and clients) that include detected vulnerability list, endpoint-by-endpoint analysis, severity classification and execution statistics
- **Backend Layer:** This layer consists of multiple system-level modules responsible for compute orchestration and persistent data management required during test-case generation. The Compute Module implements the core logic for AI-driven vulnerability test case synthesis. It handles prompt engineering, manages asynchronous communication with

the private GPT engine, aggregates multi-step AI responses, performs normalization and cleanup of generated content, and assembles the final output into a Postman-compatible test collection. The Storage Module provides persistent and structured data handling for intermediate artifacts such as raw model responses, temporary test case drafts, meta-data, and final deliverables. To improve performance and reduce redundant AI calls, the layer incorporates caching, and deduplication mechanisms. Since GPT-based inference is computationally expensive, this architecture ensures optimal resource utilization, minimizes repeated model invocations, and improves the overall throughput of the test generation pipeline.

4 Proof of Concepts and Deployment

The project is designed and developed on modular approach where generalized modules are developed with generalized interfaces to communicate and integrate with each other's. Python was used a development language where the whole concept exposes feature through external interfaces using microservice (RESTAPI) and command-line interaction approach. Microservice only facilitates to accept the OpenAPI file and then generates the test cases and environment variables list in the postman data model.

The deployment of ACME is based on highly distributed where various components deployed in separate containers, ACME service, ACME web module, compute modules and GPT services are deployed in individual containers. Figure 4 shows the deployment architecture of the project. Since the AI response is slow and takes time to process the request therefore, we introduced Redis and Worker module. It off-loads computing intensive requests from the ACME services and independently handles them. Upon successful completion, it sends links to the downloadable files to the requesters by email. The GPT service, as shown in the deployment figure, is a RISE deployed AI service in the cloud environment, for RISE employees and partners. As I mentioned above that the client has both options to communicate with ACME service using web module or command-line tool. The web server only accepts OpenAPI file and then generates postman compatible test cases. If a user, want to execute those then cases then he has to provide required values in the environment variables and then use the command line tool for execution and report generation.

Figure 5 shows the web interface of the project which facilitates software developers and cybersecurity engineers to select a valid OpenAPI json file which defines templates of various endpoints, data objects and required parameters. On the web interface user have to provide email address so once the test cases are ready then MicroSecAI will send email to the requester to download. User has also options to select the vulnerabilities against they wants to test the RESTAPI, which makes the system more configurable and focus on the required test cases.

Figure 4: Deployment architecture of MicoSecAI and connection between various containers

ACME VULNERABILITY TESTCASES GENERATOR

Upload File

Browse... updatemedicalreport.yaml

Selected: updatemedicalreport.yaml

Email Address

Select Vulnerabilities

- API1:2023 - Broken Object Level Authorization
- API2:2023 - Broken Authentication
- API3:2023 - Broken Object Property Level Authorization
- API4:2023 - Unrestricted Resource Consumption
- API5:2023 - Broken Function Level Authorization
- API6:2023 - Unrestricted Access to Sensitive Business Flows
- API7:2023 - Server Side Request Forgery
- API8:2023 - Security Misconfiguration
- API9:2023 - Improper Inventory Management
- API10:2023 - Unsafe Consumption of APIs

Generate Security Testcases

Figure 5: Web interface of ACME (MicroSecAI) to upload OpenAPI file for generating vulnerability test cases

As I mentioned above that the client has both options to communicate with ACME service using web module or command-line tool. The web server only accepts OpenAPI file and then generates postman compatible test cases. For test cases execution, values of the environment variables should be specified, then use the command line tool for execution and report generation.

5 Conclusions

Automation and awareness are critical enablers in cybersecurity for the effective adoption of the shift-left approach within the software development lifecycle. Although certain security checks are already automated, the generation of comprehensive test cases remains a complex and largely manual task. This process often requires cybersecurity experts to design scenarios, develop test cases, and execute them to identify potential vulnerabilities.

In the ACME project, we focused on leveraging AI models and property-based testing approaches to automatically generate security test cases for microservices. These test cases evaluate services against a spectrum of vulnerabilities, ranging from simple to complex. The proposed pipeline, implemented as a MicroSecAI module, not only assesses known vulnerabilities but also systematically explores edge and corner cases, thereby improving the security, robustness, and resilience of microservices against diverse attack vectors.

The performance of the system depends on the size of the input OpenAPI specification, as each endpoint is processed individually to generate relevant test cases. Consequently, the total number of generated test cases is highly dependent on the number of endpoints provided to the MicroSecAI module. For example, the sample described in Section 5 contains five endpoints, for which the system generates between twelve and twenty test cases per endpoint, depending on the responses produced by the AI engine.

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Appendix A

Appendix A.1

Availability of Source Code and Sample Files

The software presented in this study has been developed in Python and is currently in testing phase, therefore, being maintained in a private Git repository. Researchers interested in evaluating or using the software may request access by contacting the first author of this paper via email.

The repository also includes a sample OpenAPI JSON specification containing multiple endpoints, which are used to conduct rigorous vulnerability assessments as part of the proposed approach.

Listing 1: OpenAPI specification

```
1 "post": "/v1/medical/report/store"
2 "post": "/v1/medical/report/deserialize"
3 "get" : "/v1/medical/report/find"
4 "get" : "/v1/medical/report/export/{id}"
5 "get" : "/v1/medical/report/export-csv"
6 "get" : "/v1/medical/report/export-csv/{id}"
7 "get" : "/v1/medical/report/export-all"
```